

A Neuro-Symbolic Framework for Safely Applying LLMs in Human-Automation Co-Driving

Safayat Bin Hakim, Wenkai Tan, Shouhuai Xu, Houbing Herbert Song

Abstract—Large Language Models (LLMs) have demonstrated contextual reasoning capabilities in autonomous driving, yet their opaque decision-making and insufficient robustness hinder deployment in safety-critical human-automation co-driving. To address this issue, we propose a neuro-symbolic framework where LLMs provide contextual reasoning outside of the safety-critical loop while auditable symbolic constraints ensure invariant guarantees, advancing trustworthy intelligent transportation. The framework assures that authority allocation is formalized as blended control, while automation authority is verified against temporal constraints before execution. This is achieved by letting the symbolic layer project LLM-proposed authorities onto constraint-satisfying envelopes, thereby enforcing safety invariants with transparent explanations anchored to verifiable monitor signals. We prove that the framework assures emergency monotonicity and bounded takeover variation properties, independent of LLM correctness. We further show that these guarantees hold even if LLMs behave pathologically.

Index Terms—Neuro-symbolic AI, authority allocation, human-automation co-driving, large language models, signal temporal logic, formal verification

I. INTRODUCTION

HUMAN-automation co-driving is emerging as a pragmatic pathway for deploying autonomy under uncertainty, enabling fluid responsibility transitions between driver and automation based on context, driver state, and system confidence. Recent studies [1], [2] demonstrate that Large Language Models (LLMs) excel at high-level reasoning and natural language interaction, which are essential to personalized driving assistance. For instance, Talk2Drive [3], which uses LLM-driven verbal interaction, can reduce takeover rates by 65.2% when providing advisory guidance rather than safety-verified authority allocation. Although LLMs offer contextual adaptability, their black-box nature, hallucination tendency, and vulnerability to attacks and distribution shift [4], [5] render their applications to safety-critical handoff decisions questionable.

Classical *authority allocation* (i.e., the dynamic process determining whether the human driver or the autonomous driving system should have control over a car) employs game-theoretic optimization with Control Barrier Functions (CBF) and Control Lyapunov Functions (CLF), solving convex quadratic programs for optimal authority allocation (i.e., distribution) [6],

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[7]. These approaches satisfy formal safety constraints, but lack semantic reasoning about *why* handoffs occur and cannot achieve formally safe, context-aware, explainable authority allocation.

This gap creates deployment barriers. Drivers cannot trust opaque LLM recommendations. Without formal verification, LLM commands may violate safety invariants during emergencies [8], [9]. Regulatory frameworks (e.g., ISO 26262 [10], UN R157 [11]) cannot certify systems lacking provable safety properties. To address these challenges, we propose a novel approach: letting LLMs act as a *policy adviser* that proposes structured authority intents with explanations, while projecting LLM outputs onto constraint-satisfying envelopes and using a symbolic monitor to enforce temporal constraints via Signal Temporal Logic (STL) [12], [13]. This keeps LLMs outside of the safety-critical control loop while leveraging their contextual reasoning, leading to certifiable systems.

Contributions. This paper makes three contributions. (i) We propose a novel *monitorable interface* that constrains LLMs to structured authority intents amenable to formal monitoring. (ii) We propose a neuro-symbolic formalization to cast shared control as constrained decision process that takes inputs including STL-monitored safety signals. (iii) We prove safety properties with emergency monotonicity and bounded variation independent of LLM reliability, while providing evaluation protocol aligned with functional safety practices. We have made our implementation available at <https://github.com/sbhakim/neuro-symbolic-driving>.

II. RELATED WORK

LLMs for Autonomous Driving. Recent surveys [1], [2], [14] categorize LLM applications into perception, planning, and coordination of autonomous driving. For instance, DriveGPT4-V2 [15] demonstrates closed-loop driving, while acknowledging models lack commercial readiness. Critical gaps remain in formal safety assurance [4]. The present study makes a first step towards bridging these gaps.

STL (Signal Temporal Logic) for Verification. STL provides quantitative robustness semantics over continuous signals to enable runtime monitoring for safety-critical systems [12], [13], formalize traffic rules [8], encode Responsibility-Sensitive Safety rules [9], guide safe autonomous-vehicle navigation [16], and enable gradient-based learning [17]. These studies are complementary to the present one as our framework can leverage them as building-blocks.

Neuro-Symbolic Artificial Intelligence (AI). Neuro-symbolic approaches combine neural learning with symbolic reasoning

to achieve the best of both worlds in terms of robustness and interpretability [18]. For instance, Deep Reinforcement Learning has been integrated with Symbolic Logic to achieve safe highway driving [19]. Our work makes a significant contribution in applying neuro-symbolic principles to tackle LLM-based authority allocation in human-automation co-driving.

Authority Allocation in Shared Control. Two closely related prior studies are [6], which proposes game-theoretic authority allocation via CBF-CLF optimization, and [7], which considers dynamic indirect shared control. While mathematically rigorous, these studies lack contextual reasoning and natural language interaction, both of which are addressed in the present study via the employment of LLMs.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. Modeling Authority as Continuous Blending Variable

Let \mathbb{N} denote the set of natural numbers and \mathbb{R} denote the set of real numbers. Consider discrete time $k \in \mathbb{N}$ with sampling period $\Delta > 0$. Let vehicle state $x_k \in \mathbb{R}^n$ comprise position, velocity, and yaw, where $n = 4$. Let o_k denote observations (perception, driver monitoring, map context). Human driver provides input $u_k^H \in \mathbb{R}^m$ (steering, acceleration) where $m = 2$, and autonomous driving process proposes $u_k^A \in \mathbb{R}^m$ from a conventional controller conditioned on o_k .

Definition 1 (Authority-Blended Control). *Define authority level $\alpha_k \in [0, 1]$ where $\alpha_k = 0$ denotes full human control and $\alpha_k = 1$ full autonomous driving. The executed control is:*

$$u_k = \alpha_k u_k^A + (1 - \alpha_k) u_k^H \quad (1)$$

with closed-loop dynamics:

$$x_{k+1} = f(x_k, u_k, w_k) \quad (2)$$

where w_k represents disturbances and modeling error.

B. Modeling Safety Specification via Continuous Signals and Discrete Invariants

We encode safety requirements as STL formula φ over continuous signals $d(t)$ (distance-to-obstacle), $\text{TTC}(t)$ (time-to-collision), $v(t)$ (speed) using standard STL semantics [12] with robustness $\rho(\varphi, \xi) \in \mathbb{R}$, where $\rho > 0$ implies satisfaction with margin. The continuous-signal safety specification is:

$$\varphi_{\text{continuous}} := \mathbf{G}_{[0, T]}(d(t) \geq d_{\min}). \quad (3)$$

Let $d_k := d(k\Delta)$ and $\text{TTC}_k := \text{TTC}(k\Delta)$ denote sampled values. Then, the authority dynamics are governed by discrete-time monitor invariants.

Let $e_k \in \{0, 1\}$ denote the emergency indicator, e.g., $e_k = \mathbb{I}[\text{TTC}_k \leq \tau]$. The monitor enforces:

$$\alpha_{k+1} \geq \alpha_k \quad \text{if } e_k = 1 \quad (\text{emergency monotonicity}) \quad (4)$$

$$|\alpha_{k+1} - \alpha_k| \leq \gamma \Delta \quad \text{for all } k \quad (\text{bounded rate}), \quad (5)$$

where γ is the maximum authority-rate parameter (unit: s^{-1} where s stands for second). Constraint (4) prevents authority from decreasing during collision risk, while constraint (5)

bounds the rate for preventing driving authority oscillation (i.e., takeovers).

C. LLM Authority Intent Schema

Let z_k denote structured *authority intent* emitted by LLM:

$$z_k \in \mathcal{Z} = \{\text{INCREASE, DECREASE, HOLD, CONFIRM, FALLBACK}\} \times \mathbb{R}, \quad (6)$$

where the real component specifies target $\hat{\alpha}_k \in [0, 1]$ or rate limit. Note that the LLM does *not* output u_k^A or u_k ; it only recommends how authority should evolve and provide justification for human interface.

D. Problem Statement

Given system state (x_k, o_k) and safety specification $\varphi_{\text{continuous}}$ and discrete invariants (4)–(5), design authority allocation policy $\pi : (x_k, o_k) \rightarrow \alpha_{k+1}$ that: (1) generates context-aware recommendations using LLM-enabled reasoning; (2) verifies LLM-generated recommendations against specifications with robustness margin $\delta > 0$; (3) provides transparent explanations anchoring LLM-enabled reasoning to monitor signals; and (4) operates within real-time constraints.

IV. NEURO-SYMBOLIC FRAMEWORK ARCHITECTURE

A. System Overview and Design Principles

Our solution is a novel neuro-symbolic framework, which achieves the best of two approaches as follows: Traditional control approaches satisfy constraints but lack contextual reasoning; whereas, pure LLM approaches provide adaptability but lack formal guarantees.

Figure 1 illustrates our architecture decomposing authority allocation into two complementary layers: a *neural layer* employing LLMs for context-aware reasoning, and a *symbolic layer* enforcing safety constraints via STL verification and discrete-time monitor invariants. The neural layer processes multimodal inputs (scene descriptions, driver state, telemetry) generating authority recommendations $\alpha_{\text{rec}}(k)$ with natural language rationales. The symbolic layer verifies $\alpha_{\text{rec}}(k)$ against STL specification $\varphi_{\text{continuous}}$ and discrete invariants (4)–(5), computing robustness margins and projecting to admissible authorities when violations occur. A blended control module implements verified authority $\alpha^*(k)$ via (1).

Our architecture design adheres to four principles. (i) **Modularity**: neural and symbolic components operate independently enabling separate certification. (ii) **Safety-First**: symbolic layer has veto authority. (iii) **Explainability**: each decision includes LLM reasoning plus verification certificate. (iv) **Incremental Deployment**: the framework supports gradual transition from advisory to shared control.

B. Monitor-Enforceable Authority Update

Let \mathcal{E}_k denote the STL-derived envelope constraint set:

$$\mathcal{E}_k = \{\alpha \in [0, 1] : \psi(\alpha; x_k, o_k) \geq 0\}, \quad (7)$$

where ψ is a short-horizon conservative surrogate for STL robustness $\rho(\varphi_{\text{continuous}}, \xi)$. Specifically, ψ is obtained by: (i)

Neuro-Symbolic Authority Allocation Architecture

Fig. 1. The proposed neuro-symbolic architecture: LLM generates structured authority intents and explanations; symbolic monitor verifies them against STL constraints and discrete invariants and projects them onto safe envelope; control executes verified authority

linearizing the short-horizon rollout of (2) around nominal controls (u_k^A, u_k^H); (ii) evaluating differentiable STL robustness [17] and taking first-order lower bound, yielding:

$$\psi(\alpha; x_k, o_k) \approx b_k + a_k \alpha \geq 0 \quad (8)$$

with scalar a_k, b_k updated online. The discrete invariants (4)–(5) define:

$$\mathcal{I}_k := \{\alpha : |\alpha - \alpha_k| \leq \gamma \Delta\} \cap \begin{cases} [\alpha_k, 1] & \text{if } e_k = 1 \\ [0, 1] & \text{if } e_k = 0 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

The complete safe set is:

$$\mathcal{S}_k = \mathcal{E}_k \cap \mathcal{I}_k. \quad (10)$$

In our simulation, the monitor enforces discrete invariants (emergency monotonicity and bounded rate) using TTC-threshold emergency flags and headway robustness $\rho_k = d_k - d_{\min}$. Our simulation focuses on invariant enforcement and stress-testing under adversarial intent generation, while leaving the general case of α -parameterized envelope $\psi(\alpha)$ to future work.

The LLM emits intent $z_k = (\text{type}, \theta_k)$, where θ_k specifies target $\hat{\alpha}_k$ or rate limit. The *proposed* update is:

$$\tilde{\alpha}_{k+1} = \begin{cases} \text{clip}(\alpha_k + \eta(\hat{\alpha}_k - \alpha_k), 0, 1) & \text{INC/DEC} \\ \alpha_k & \text{HOLD/CONF} \\ \alpha_{\text{fb}}(x_k, o_k) & \text{FALLBACK} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where $\eta \in (0, 1]$ controls authority inertia and α_{fb} is conservative fallback.

The monitor implements projection:

$$\alpha_{k+1} = \arg \min_{\alpha \in \mathcal{S}_k} (\alpha - \tilde{\alpha}_{k+1})^2 \quad (12)$$

Under (8), this reduces to interval projection; for richer monitors it becomes a small QP feasible for real-time systems [6]. Algorithm 1 summarizes the monitor logic.

Algorithm 1 Neuro-Symbolic Monitor for Authority Allocation

Require: State x_k , observations o_k , controls u_k^H, u_k^A , authority α_k

- 1: Compute context summary $c_k \leftarrow \kappa(o_{0:k})$
- 2: LLM outputs intent z_k and explanation (for interface only)
- 3: Compute proposal $\tilde{\alpha}_{k+1}$ via (11)
- 4: Compute emergency flag $e_k = \mathbb{I}[\text{TTC}_k \leq \tau]$
- 5: Optionally compute envelope constraints (e.g., short-horizon robustness surrogate); in our simulator we use $\rho_k = d_k - d_{\min}$ and TTC thresholds
- 6: Define invariants \mathcal{I}_k via (9); compute safe set \mathcal{S}_k from constraint composition
- 7: Project: $\alpha_{k+1} \leftarrow \arg \min_{\alpha \in \mathcal{S}_k} (\alpha - \tilde{\alpha}_{k+1})^2$
- 8: Execute blended control $u_k \leftarrow \alpha_k u_k^A + (1 - \alpha_k) u_k^H$

Ensure: Monitor-feasible authority α_{k+1}

V. SAFETY PROPERTIES

We state monitor-level properties independent of LLM correctness because these properties are *interface guarantees*, meaning: if the monitor is implemented correctly, they hold even when the LLM is misleading or inconsistent.

A. Emergency Monotonicity Property

Property 1. Assume the monitor enforces (4). Let $[k_0, k_1]$ be a maximal emergency interval with $e_k = 1$ for all $k \in [k_0, k_1]$. Then, we have:

$$\alpha_{k_0} \leq \alpha_{k_0+1} \leq \dots \leq \alpha_{k_1+1} \quad (13)$$

Proof. For any $k \in [k_0, k_1]$, $e_k = 1$ enforces $\alpha_{k+1} \geq \alpha_k$ via (4). Chaining inequalities yields the claim. \square

Property 1 can be understood as follows. During an emergency, autonomous driving authority never decreases, ensuring progressive engagement of safety assistance rather than abrupt authority transfers that overwhelm human drivers.

B. Bounded Takeover Variation Property

Define the total variation as $\text{TV}_N(\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} |\alpha_{k+1} - \alpha_k|$.

Property 2. *If the monitor enforces (5), then we have:*

$$\text{TV}_N(\alpha) \leq N\gamma\Delta = \gamma T, \quad T := N\Delta \quad (14)$$

Proof. By (5), each summand satisfies $|\alpha_{k+1} - \alpha_k| \leq \gamma\Delta$. Summation yields (14). \square

Property 2 can be understood as follows. Eq.(14) bounds cumulative authority churn, limiting oscillations that degrade comfort and trust—a monitor guarantee requiring no assumptions about LLM behavior.

C. Soundness of Projection

Proposition 1. *The projected authority α_{k+1} from (12) satisfies all constraints enforced by the monitor in \mathcal{S}_k . In particular, the discrete invariants (4)–(5) and any configured authority floors hold by construction.*

Proof. By definition, (12) optimizes over $\alpha \in \mathcal{S}_k$. Thus, α_{k+1} is feasible and satisfies constraints from \mathcal{E}_k and \mathcal{I}_k . \square

Assumption 1 (Envelope Soundness). *The surrogate ψ conservatively lower-bounds true STL robustness over prediction horizon h when $\psi(\alpha; x_k, o_k) \geq \delta$. Thus, we have $\rho(\varphi_{\text{continuous}}, \xi_{k:k+h}^\alpha) \geq \delta - \epsilon$, where ϵ is approximation error.*

Corollary 1 (Local Robustness). *Under Assumption 1 with $\epsilon < \delta$, if the monitor enforces $\psi(\alpha_{k+1}; x_k, o_k) \geq \delta$ at each step, then each h -step prediction maintains positive STL robustness $\rho(\varphi_{\text{continuous}}, \xi_{k:k+h}^{\alpha_{k+1}}) > 0$.*

Remark. Proposition 1 guarantees feasibility with respect to the conservative envelope. Corollary 1 provides local robustness over the prediction horizon. Global safety additionally requires receding-horizon recomputation with bounded model error, validated through simulation.

D. LLM Contract and Explanation Anchoring

The LLM operates behind a *contract* constraining outputs: (i) `intent_type` \in {INCREASE, DECREASE, HOLD, CONFIRM, FALLBACK}; (ii) `target_alpha` \in $[0, 1]$; (iii) `risk_rationale` referencing monitor signals (e.g., `TTC_low`, `headway_tight`); and (iv) `confidence` \in $[0, 1]$ as communication primitive, but not safety certificate. Explanations must be *anchored* to monitor variables: “requesting confirmation because TTC is near τ and lane-offset variance increased.” When the monitor overrides $\tilde{\alpha}_{k+1}$, the interface displays the monitor decision as authoritative cause (e.g., “authority increase enforced due to emergency monotonicity”), preventing misleading justifications.

VI. SIMULATION-BASED VALIDATION

We validate the framework through closed-loop simulation comparing three scenarios: (B1) classical rule-based, (B2) LLM-only (no monitor), (B3) neuro-symbolic (ours). To demonstrate the robustness of our framework, we consider three threats against the adopted LLMs: (i) ambiguous or adversarial language; (ii) corrupted text channels such as prompt injection and instruction hijacking; and (iii) inconsistent or poisoned context summaries. To mitigate these threats, we consider the following countermeasures: structured schema parsing; strict rejection of out-of-schema outputs; input sanitization; rate limiting; and safety monitor projection (12) and keeping the trusted computing base small and auditable per ISO 26262 [5], [10].

A. Simulation

The simulator implements discrete-time dynamics (2) with $\Delta = 0.1$ s (seconds), PD automation controller, delayed human controller ($\tau_{\text{delay}} = 0.3$ s), and projection-based monitor (Algorithm 1). The parameters are: $\eta = 0.3$, $\gamma = 0.5 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\tau_{\text{emerg}} = 2.0$ s, $d_{\text{min}} = 10.0$ m. For RealLLM simulation, we use the OpenAI API model `gpt-4.1-mini` for structured intent generation. To evaluate robustness, we additionally run adversarial intent generation modes (e.g., force-decrease / oscillation) that intentionally output pathological intents to stress-test the symbolic monitor. Emergency windows are defined by $\text{TTC}(t) \leq \tau_{\text{emerg}}$. We report both nominal and stress-test runs.

B. Emergency Braking and Robustness Stress Test

The lead vehicle follows a braking profile inducing emergency windows, with repeated episodes in the stress-test variant to trigger oscillatory or adversarial LLM intents. Fig. 2 validates monitor invariants under this setting (TTC clipped to $[0, 10]$ s for readability). Initial conditions: 30m separation, ego at 30 m/s, $\alpha_0 = 0.2$.

Figure 2 empirically validates the monitor-level guarantees across all four panels under the same vehicle dynamics and lead-vehicle scenario while varying the intent generator (nominal vs. adversarial) to stress-test invariant enforcement. Elaborations follow.

Property 1 Validation. Panel (a): LLM-only violates constraint (4) multiple times during emergency (red X markers), decreasing authority during emergency ($\text{TTC} \leq \tau_{\text{emerg}}$). Neuro-symbolic enforces $\alpha_{k+1} \geq \alpha_k$ via projection (12) throughout all emergency windows by projecting the proposed update onto the invariant-satisfying set.

STL Safety Margins. Panels (b–c) show that adversarial intent outputs can drive the system closer to the constraint boundary (reduced robustness), while NeSy maintains improved robustness margins relative to LLM-only by enforcing invariant-safe authority updates.

Property 2 Validation. Panel (d): Total variation TV remains below γT for neuro-symbolic, validating bound (14). LLM-only can exceed the theoretical limit under adversarial/oscillatory intent outputs, while NeSy remains bounded by

VII. DISCUSSION

A. Deployment

Real-world deployment demands safety guarantees. Recent LLM-for-driving surveys emphasize that LLMs add value in semantic reasoning and interaction but remain difficult to certify as direct controllers [1], [2]. Our framework keeps LLMs outside of the safety-critical control loop and reduces the trusted computing base to a specification-driven auditable monitor, consistent with functional safety practice [10]. That is, our framework makes LLMs act as a co-driving manager: it interprets driver preferences, explains authority shifts, and selects from a finite intent set, while the monitor guarantees invariant handoff behavior. Thus, our framework offers realistic progression from advisory mode with confirmation prompts to tighter automation authority in well-defined operational design domains as verification envelopes and datasets mature. Current regulatory momentum (UNECE R157, ISO 26262 updates, regional Level 3/4 approvals) supports this timeline [20].

Moreover, our framework supports incremental deployment aligned with technological maturity and regulatory evolution. This suggests us to propose a three-phase progression:

- **Advisory Co-Pilot:** LLMs provide authority recommendations via natural language while drivers retain full control (Level 2 ADAS).
- **Supervised Shared Control:** system implements verified authority allocation with dynamic control sharing (Level 3 conditional automation on highways).
- **Certified Adaptive Co-Driving:** fully certified neuro-symbolic allocation with formal safety assurance enables complex urban deployment (Level 4 high automation in well-defined operational design domains).

The automation levels referenced above follow the SAE J3016 taxonomy [21].

B. Limitations and Future Directions

The present study has five limitations, which represent opportunities for future research. First, LLMs suffer from hallucination (generating plausible but incorrect reasoning), limited spatial reasoning for complex geometries, and vulnerability to adversarial inputs (prompt injection, scene description poisoning). Future work should investigate mitigations, including: employing structured output schema and symbolic constraint enforcement; integrating adversarial training and input sanitization layers.

Second, verification scalability presents a challenge as STL evaluation scales polynomially with specification complexity and time horizon. For nested temporal operators over long horizons, approximation techniques or compositional verification may be required.

Third, driver acceptance remains an open empirical question. Human factors studies are essential to validate that neuro-symbolic explanations improve trust calibration versus pure neural or symbolic approaches. Longitudinal studies measuring appropriate reliance across diverse driver populations constitute critical future work.

Fig. 2. Robustness stress-test validation of neuro-symbolic authority allocation. (a) Authority level α_k for Classical (B1), LLM-only (B2), and NeSy (ours); shaded regions denote emergency windows where $TTC(t) \leq \tau_{\text{emerg}} = 2.0$ s. Red \times markers indicate emergency monotonicity violations by LLM-only (authority decreases during emergency). (b) Headway distance $d(t)$ and $TTC(t)$ with safety constraint $d_{\text{min}} = 10$ m and emergency threshold τ_{emerg} (TTC clipped to $[0, 10]$ s; infinite values omitted). (c) STL robustness $\rho(\varphi, \xi)$ with violation threshold at $\rho = 0$ (positive values satisfy specification with safety margin). (d) Cumulative total variation $TV_N(\alpha)$ compared against theoretical bound γT where $\gamma = 0.5 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

construction. This confirms rate limiting independent of LLM behavior.

C. Comparison with Existing Approaches

Table I shows that our framework is unique in combining context-awareness, formal safety, and explainability; whereas, existing approaches only achieve these properties partially. In contrast to rule-based methods, our framework achieves contextual reasoning when handling corner cases traditional rules miss (e.g., driver fatigue with adverse weather). In contrast to optimization-only approaches, our framework uses natural language explanations to improve human comprehension. In contrast to pure LLM systems, our framework uses formal verification to prevent safety violations through monitor-enforced constraints.

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF AUTHORITY ALLOCATION APPROACHES

Approach	Context-Aware	Formal Safety	Explainable
Rule-based [6]	No	Yes	No
CBF-CLF QP [7]	No	Yes	No
Pure LLM [3]	Yes	No	Partial
Ours (Neuro-Symbolic)	Yes	Yes	Yes

Fourth, multi-agent coordination represents a natural extension. Current formulation addresses single-vehicle authority allocation. Extension to cooperative multi-vehicle scenarios (V2V authority negotiation) requires Byzantine-robust communication protocols and consensus mechanisms for distributed authority allocation decisions.

Fifth, the framework can be more thoroughly validated via the metrics defined in Table II. Moreover, language stress tests will assess paraphrase invariance, ambiguity tolerance, and adversarial instruction resistance. Ablation studies will systematically isolate emergency monotonicity, rate bounds, projection versus rejection, and STL specification variants toward ISO 26262 functional safety validation.

TABLE II
EVALUATION METRICS FOR CO-DRIVING AUTHORITY ALLOCATION

Category	Metric
Safety (hard)	STL satisfaction rate $\mathbb{I}[\rho(\varphi, \xi) > 0]$; minimum robustness $\min_k \rho_k$; collision count (lower better)
Authority dynamics	Takeover count; total variation $TV_N(\alpha)$; emergency monotonicity violations (lower better); recovery time to safe authority
Comfort	Jerk norm $\ \dot{a}\ _\infty$ (lower better); steering rate $\ \dot{\delta}\ _\infty$ (lower better); completion time
Explanation quality	Anchoring rate: fraction referencing monitor signals; faithfulness: agreement between stated causes and monitor decisions; calibration: abstain/CONFIRM frequency under uncertainty

VIII. CONCLUSION

We presented a novel neuro-symbolic framework for safe authority allocation in human-automation co-driving, with the key idea of confining LLMs to structured authority intents and using a symbolic monitor to enforce temporal logic invariants. The projection-based monitor yields interface guarantees—emergency monotonicity and bounded variation—independent of LLM reliability, proven theoretically and validated under adversarial stress-testing where the LLM behaves pathologically. Our formalization casts shared control as blended execution where authority is verified against STL-monitored safety signals before implementation. The framework provides global guarantees through discrete invariants and local robustness over prediction horizons under conservative envelope approximation. Closed-loop simulation demonstrates safety preservation across emergency braking scenarios with quantified robustness margins. We proposed a three-phase roadmap for deploying the framework in the real world. We discussed limitations of the present study and future research directions.

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